

ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK IN READING CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

The article provides general information about the aspects related to pedagogical technologies and the methods of their application in the development of their thinking and successful performance of this work through reading lessons for primary classes.

INTRODUCTION

At a time when the field of education is rapidly developing in our country, establishing its school stage on the basis of a perfect mechanism remains one of the urgent issues. In particular, the use of existing innovative methods of pedagogical technologies in the process of education of primary grades is one of the needs of modern education.

The subject of reading in the primary grades of general secondary education teaches students to read consciously, correctly and expressively, while forming in them the culture of reading and speaking, as well as the ability to think independently. It serves to develop students in all aspects.

MAIN PART

It is known that reading literacy is directly related to people's goals for studying. More broadly, these reasons or goals include enjoyment, self-interested learning, and community participation. When most young readers are just beginning to read, they read mostly narrative texts (such as stories or picture books) or information-rich texts that inform and answer questions about the world around them. As young students develop reading literacy, and according to research, this literacy requires that students learn to read, so reading and getting information from books and other printed materials is becoming important.

Here, the concept of reading literacy has a broad meaning. The purpose of this course is for the student to understand the text of a given artistic work, biography, letter, document, articles from newspapers and magazines, various manuals, geographical maps, etc. it is to determine their competencies such as being able to think about the content, evaluate the content of the text and give their own opinion about what they have read.

In the tests, the main attention is paid to the fact that the students know the most basic concepts in these areas, acquire basic knowledge and skills, and are able to use them in real life situations! these tests are not intended to test the knowledge of students on specific topics during the lesson!

PISA tests use four different test methods:

- a) One-answer tests;
- b) Multiple answer tests;
- c) Questions with short or detailed answers;
- d) The student's opinion on the solution of a problem (usually such questions have general answers, the student's answer is not required to exactly match the answer of the test structure, the student's creativity is supported).

The main task of reading classes in the process of literacy training is to introduce students to sounds and letters, to teach them their correct pronunciation, to help children learn to read correctly, quickly, consciously and expressively. consists of forming skills. Also, this period has a special place with its responsibility in enriching students' vocabulary, developing their connected speech, enriching their knowledge, forming their thinking, listening, and receiving intuition.

The main goal of teaching the science of reading in primary grades: to form the spiritual and moral world, literary and aesthetic taste of students through the teaching of rare examples of national and world literature, as well as the knowledge of independent thinking, figurative thinking, formation and development of skills; it is to expand and strengthen the spirituality and worldview of students by making students interested in fiction, by forming the world and human nature, national and universal values, as well as reading culture in the process of teaching works.

The main task of teaching the subject of reading (grades 1-4):

- to ensure the formation and development of students' oral speech based on the standards of literary language, to develop speech competence; high literacy in written speech, compliance with the standards of literary language, development of skills and abilities to use stylistic diversity, first familiar, then unfamiliar text expression is taught, skills and competence of the student are determined. Quantitative indicators are also determined - reading speed, conscious and fluent reading, how many words can be read in one minute.

The goal is for the child to fully read and retell the content of the text, as well as listen to and understand the speech of others. The works on the topic of the motherland included in this program will help to familiarize the students with the socio-political, cultural and educational life of our country and the creative work of our people.

At the end of the academic year of the 1st grade, children read small works about the Motherland and its nature and human values.

In the 2nd grade, they get acquainted with works about the Motherland, mother nature, independence, people's life and work, moral relations, which are not very complicated in terms of form and content.

In the 3rd and 4th grade curriculum, the scope of topics is much wider.

In these classes, a large part of the reading lessons is focused on reading the work and working on the text.

In the lesson, using methods that increase students' activity and enrich their imagination, reading works based on the content of the genre and dividing them into roles, retelling the story on behalf of the characters, continuing the story about the hero's fate, and using positive tasks such as creating an oral story on interesting topics such things are done.

In these lessons, it is possible to use the following technologies as solutions that determine the relevance of our sub-topic and the main issue:

- "Technology of teaching writing in the period of literacy education";
- Deep study of these issues is the main goal of the teaching technology based on "Case Study". This technology helps to strengthen the knowledge of the studied subject in the process of solving practical situations, acquire the skills of analyzing problems and accepting aspects individually or in groups, creative and learning abilities, logical thinking, speech and environmental conditions. helps develop adaptive skills and independent decision-making and self-control.

In order to develop students' thinking, the teacher, when preparing for the lesson, chooses the types of tasks, determines the material of the lesson and the mental activity exercises that the students will perform in mastering it.

Of course, in this process, reading outside the classroom also serves to determine the chronological content of the work by looking at the books, cover, title page, introduction, table of contents and pictures of an unfamiliar author. Instilling in children love of goodness, hatred of evil, development of coherent speech, and raising of literary and aesthetic thinking is the essence of reading classes.

CONCLUSION

In a word, the subject of "Reading" in the primary grade is to expand students' thinking activities, to be able to think freely, to understand the opinions of others, to be able to express their thoughts fluently orally and in writing, society being able to communicate freely with members serves skills and competencies.

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